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PREVENTION OF ALVEOLAR RIDGE ATROPHY AND DEFORMATIES AFTER TOOTH EXTRACTION. (An article review)

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ABSTRACT

This article summarizes the main features of GBR for the prevention of an atrophy of alveolar ridge and gives brief information about using various methods for its prevention. A comparative analysis of methods for maintaining the topographical features of the ridge carried out, which we concluded that most proper options and alternative treatment protocols that improving the outcomes of clinicians in choosing the most capable treatment.

Keywords: prevention of atrophy, resorption of alveolar ridge, types of osteoplastic materials.

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ПРОФИЛАКТИКА АТРОФИИ И ДЕФОРМАЦИИ АЛЬВЕОЛЯРНОГО ОТРОСТКА ПОСЛЕ УДАЛЕНИЯ ЗУБОВ (Обзорная статья)

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье обобщаются биологические основы и компоненты НКР для предотвращения атрофии альвеолярного гребня, а также приводятся научно обоснованные рекомендации для рассмотрения стоматологами с использованием различных методов для ее профилактики. Был проведен сравнительный анализ методов сохранения высоты альвеолярного гребня, исходя из этого мы получили что варианты и альтернативы протоколов лечения улучшают исходы клиницистов в выборе оптимального лечения.

Ключевые слова: профилактика атрофии, резорбция альвеолярного гребня, виды

остеопластических материалов.

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ТИШЛАР ОЛИНГАНДАН СУНГ АЛЬВЕОЛЯР УСИГНИ АТРОФИЯ ВА ДЕФОРМАЦИЯ ПРОФИЛАКТИКАСИ (мақола шарҳи)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Ушбу мақолада альвеоляр атрофиясини олдини олиш учун юналтирилган суяк тикланишининг биологик асослари ва таркибий қисмлари умумлаштирилади, шунингдек, стоматологлар томонидан унинг олдини олиш учун турли усуллардан фойдаланган ҳолда илмий асосланган тавсиялар берилди. Альвеоляр ўсиқ баландлигини сақлаб қолиш усуллари қиёсий таҳлил қилиш амалга оширилди, шунинг учун даволаш протоколларининг вариантлари ва муқобиллари клиника врачларининг optimal даволанишни танлашдаги натижаларини яхшилади.

Калит сўзлар: атрофия профилактикаси, жаг альвеоляр усигини атрофияси, остеопластик материалларни турлари

Relevance.

Alveolar ridge atrophy and morphological changes after tooth extraction have been extensively studied, and the pathophysiology is now well understood. The loss of bone support of the alveolar ridge is a major problem for dental restorative procedures. Treatments such as removable dentures rely on the ridge as the primary source of support. Fixed dentures require adequate ridge height for aesthetic, functional and adequate oral hygiene reasons. Sufficient density and morphology of the alveolar bone is a prerequisite for successful implant placement. Bone regeneration techniques promote ridge preservation and have been shown to improve outcomes in several dental procedures. To date, many studies have evaluated the components of guided bone regeneration (GBR) procedures.

Bone healing differs from other tissues in its ability to regenerate rather than form a fibroblastic scar. This healing process is divided into primary and secondary healing. Typically, both processes begin with hematoma formation and result in remodeling of tissue bone into a stronger lamellar structure. In secondary healing, which occurs when bone edges are not in close proximity (>1 mm), endochondral ossification causes an intermediate formation of a cartilaginous callus model. [3] The capacity and speed of this healing process depend on vascular perfusion, mechanical stability, space for hard tissue formation, the presence of stem cells, and isolation of the site due to close proximity of soft tissue edges. [four]

Similar to bone healing, wound healing involving the gingiva and mucosa is divided into overlapping phases. Initially, during hemostasis, a coagulate is formed and platelets are activated. These activated platelets release cytokines that attract inflammatory cells to the site of inflammation. Neutrophils accumulate during the acute phase; they eliminate pathogens, remove damaged cells, and release cytokines that cause macrophage proliferation. Macrophages perform many functions similar to those of neutrophils, in addition, they secrete cytokines that stimulate the differentiation of mesenchymal cells into fibroblasts and promote angiogenesis. These changes mark the transition to a proliferative phase during which collagen deposition, wound contraction and angiogenesis/vascularization lead to the formation of granulation tissue. Unlike bone healing, the process of epithelialization of reattachment of opposite ends of the epithelium occurs during the healing of a

laceration or surgical wound. Eventually, the maturation phase leads to replacement of granulation tissue and resorption of the wound.⁴ Wound healing by primary intention occurs when there is no gap between the edges of the laceration; however, if a large space is left during healing, the proliferative phase is lengthened, resulting in increased collagen deposition and wound contraction, which usually results in scarring, a process known as secondary intention healing.

After tooth extraction, the alveolar socket heals by secondary intention. The previously described wound healing process occurs in conjunction with secondary bone healing. [1,5] Osteoblasts and osteoclasts facilitate the regeneration/ remodeling of the bone matrix, while epithelialization attempts to isolate the site from the external environment.[4]

The simultaneous occurrence of these healing processes manifests itself as a race between epithelial isolation and osteoblastic bone regeneration. Epithelial cells often win this race due to faster apical migration than other repair cells (eg, osteoblasts). This leads to a decrease in the height of the level of the alveolar bone, the formation of a crater-like defect and a decrease in bone density in the region of the affected crest. [4,5]

Guided bone regeneration is a process used to prevent and repair ridge resorption associated with tooth loss. As discussed earlier, bone regeneration depends on several factors and requirements (vascularization, stability, space, site isolation, and stem cells). Providing these factors and meeting the requirements, in turn, creates ideal conditions for bone regeneration.

Bone grafts have been extensively studied and used to meet these requirements; grafts provide space and stability for vascularization while stimulating or providing the cellular components needed for bone formation. The graft is characterized by its mechanism as osteoconductive, osteoinductive, or osteogenesis. Osteoconductive grafts function as a scaffold for native osteoprogenitor cells for bone formation. Grafts that induce osteoblast activation via protein mediators' function through osteoinduction. Osteogenesis bone grafts contain viable osteoblasts that act on native cells to form new bone. [4,6]

Demineralized Freeze -Dried Bone Allograft (DFDBA):

For several years, the use of DFDBA has proven to be effective in HCC, reducing the degree of crestal bone loss compared to sockets without graft placement. [7,8,9] DFDBA acts as a scaffold, saving space for extraction and stabilizing the site. ultimately allowing angiogenesis. Initially, these allografts were thought to contain adequate BMP proteins to induce bone formation; however, since their introduction, numerous studies have shown that osteoinductive properties are not always inherent in the material and depend on several factors such as donor demographics. [10,11]

Tooth structure allografts:

The use of extracted teeth has recently been studied and found to have equal or slightly greater efficacy in site preservation than DFDBA. [12] Initially, an autologous tooth structure was obtained from the harvest site during the initial procedure, chaired, and immediately used as it was thought to minimize the risk of graft rejection. However, this procedure requires enough time, and the quality of the graft depends on the condition of the patient's tooth being removed. More recent studies have evaluated the use of dental tissue allografts (obtained from another person) instead of autografts. So far, they have proven to be equivalent to or slightly more successful than dental autografts, offering a new, faster, and more reliable option for clinicians. immunogenic reaction; this risk should be assessed when considering graft options on a case-by-case basis.

The ideal graft material should be biocompatible, easy to use and reliable. In addition, it must have osteoconductive, osteoinductive, and osteogenesis properties. Autogenous bone has these qualities, making it the gold standard in the NCR. [14,15] Because this graft material is taken directly from the patient, the risk of immune rejection is virtually eliminated. The surgeon will typically take material from one of several sites, including the mandibular ramus or symphysis, coronoid process, extraction socket area, maxillary tuberosity, or, if more bone is indicated, extraoral sites may be used. The decision on which plot to harvest from depends on many factors specific to each specific case. [14,15,16]

Returning to the discussion of socket healing, the exclusion of epithelial and connective tissues from bone defects allows the formation of hard tissues due to the osteogenic function of cells.

[9] For decades, barrier membranes have provided this exclusive process. Optimally, the barrier membrane should preserve the space of the bone defect by occluding soft tissue cells, it should be biocompatible with the desired handling properties, and should be either resorbable or easily removable. creation of an "ideal" membrane. Currently, there are two main types of membranes: non-resorbable and resorbable, with their own advantages and disadvantages.

Non-resorbable membranes are biocompatible and have excellent mechanical stability because they can be reinforced with titanium. In addition, they usually remain in place for a sufficient time for complete resolution. Of course, these membranes require an additional surgical procedure to remove and are associated with an increased risk of infection if contact occurs prematurely. [2] The avoidance of a repeat surgical procedure and hence the reduction in patient morbidity has drawn the attention of clinicians and researchers to resorbable membranes. However, the inability to control the rate of membrane degradation limits the duration and quality of the socket healing process. [1] Several studies comparing the use of resorbable and non-resorbable membranes in HCC found no significant difference in clinical outcomes for both. The decision on which type of membrane to use should be based on clinician preference and specific patient characteristics (immunocompetent status, religion, etc.).

Conclusion.

A vast amount of research has been done to elucidate the physiology of NKR and to develop biological materials to improve treatment strategies. To date, meta-analyses and systematic reviews of the literature have demonstrated the effectiveness of NKR procedures in preserving the ridge.^{25,26} As briefly shown in this review, there is a huge amount of variation in the way NCR is achieved. Although treatment options and alternatives improve outcomes in individual patients, they can also leave clinicians uncertain about the optimal treatment choice; in turn, which leads to a complete rejection of the protocol.

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